

AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

MODERNIZING FARMERS' EDUCATION IN THE EU: CHALLENGES AND APPROACHES

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Abstract

In EU agriculture, instead of the fragmented transmission of agricultural knowledge and information, the formation of a new system of farmer's education is based on a complex vision. Various institutional initiatives were recommended, such as integrating the concept of agricultural knowledge and information systems (AKIS) into national strategies, strengthening ties between suppliers of agricultural knowledge and innovations, developing applied research, etc. The EU AKIS principles offer a valuable framework for achieving this. They aim to modernize vocational education in agriculture, strengthen national AKIS, and create a self-sustaining network that facilitates the effective exchange of knowledge and information. This network would promote the widespread dissemination and implementation of research findings and commercial solutions among farmers, researchers, consultants, field specialists, and other stakeholders. While European countries share a common policy approach to providing knowledge and innovation to farmers, they have developed diverse models with varying degrees of success.

Keywords: agriculture, farming, farmer education, educational network, European Union

A Historical Overview

The formation of the Agricultural Knowledge and Information System (AKIS) in the European Union began in the 1960s. Initially, it was a government-supported system designed to replace the linear technology transfer model of knowledge generation in the National Agricultural Research System (NARS). In the 1980s and 1990s, the need for more active involvement of farmers and other stakeholders in the agricultural innovation process became apparent. Traditional top-down approaches to agricultural development were found to be inadequate, leading to an emphasis on participatory and decentralized approaches.

During this period, international organizations such as the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) and the International Fund for Agricultural Development (IFAD) began to popularize the concept of AKIS, which aimed to improve the effectiveness of research systems and the implementation of their results in agriculture. The AKIS concept, developed in the 1990s, focuses on the joint and coordinated activities of agricultural organizations and individuals involved in generating, transforming, transferring, storing, retrieving, integrating, disseminating, and using knowledge.

A complex network of organizations and institutions, including farmers, researchers, and extension services, advisory services, agribusinesses, and policymakers, are involved in the generation, sharing, and application of agricultural knowledge and innovation in the European Union (EU). This network is reflected in the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) plans, which serve to combine the organization and transfer of knowledge flows to individuals, organizations, and institutions that use and produce knowledge for agriculture and related fields. (1)

The AKIS approach gained further attention in the early 2000s with reports such as the World Bank's "Reaching the Rural Poor: A Renewed Strategy for Rural Development" (2) and the European Commission's "Putting Knowledge into Practice: A Broad Innovation Strategy for the EU" (3). These reports emphasized the importance of strengthening linkages between different actors in the agricultural innovation system to enhance research and its application in agriculture. The AKIS approach integrates various knowledge providers to promote the development of scientific research, the dissemination of traditional knowledge, stakeholder cooperation, and information exchange. It aims to strengthen the overall agricultural innovation process, improve the competitiveness and sustainability of the agricultural sector, and address challenges such as climate change, food security, and rural development. To achieve these goals, the AKIS concept focuses on improving cooperation and knowledge exchange between farmers, researchers, consultants, and policymakers.

Modern Trends

In the EU, the concept of the Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation System (AKIS) has become an integral part of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) for 2023-2027. It is now incorporated into the Annual Strategic Plans for Agricultural Policy (CAP SP). The new strategy outlines the need for and funding of various actions aimed at knowledge exchange and innovation. AKIS aims to integrate all participants in the system, ensuring a more efficient transfer and exchange of innovative knowledge among farmers. In the context of the EU's CAP, AKIS plays a crucial role in supporting the implementation of agricultural policies and programs, ensuring the efficient use of knowledge

and innovation for the benefit of farmers and rural communities.

The relationship between AKIS and agricultural policy is becoming crucial for enhancing innovation, sustainability, and competitiveness in the agricultural sector. In the EU, the Agricultural Innovation System (AIS), which is a network of organizations, enterprises, and individuals focused on the economic use of new products, processes, and organizational forms, emphasizes innovation over knowledge transfer. This is the dominant political direction in supporting farmers. Farmers, researchers, policymakers, and field experts work together to identify challenges, develop innovative solutions, and implement policies that benefit the agricultural sector and rural communities.

AKIS is based on the implementation of four types of interventions: 1. Knowledge exchange, dissemination of information, and promotion of innovation through training and various forms of advice and knowledge transfer, including extensive media engagement; 2. Development of advisory services for farmers by promoting interconnected services of advisors, researchers, farmer organizations, and other relevant stakeholders; 3. Promotion of innovative projects by operational groups (OG); 4. Effective use of information and communication technologies in agriculture and rural areas to improve knowledge sharing. Such agricultural policies aim to ensure the development of sustainable agriculture in Europe. The scientific literature describes these interventions and the expected outcomes. It is important to focus on these policy components, organizational functions, and the roles of different actors, as well as practical guidelines for developing and implementing innovative agricultural projects. (4) Trends and challenges of agricultural innovation systems and the role of public policies and institutions in promoting innovation and technology transfer are also broadly characterized. (5)

Comparative analysis

Several European countries and regions have implemented policies and programs influenced by AKIS adapted to their contexts. AKIS can vary from country to country and these differences depend on specific environmental, social, geomorphological, and cultural aspects of contextual situations.

- The structure of the AKIS system in EU countries varies according to how centralized the system is. The production and dissemination of agricultural information are usually coordinated by government agencies or research institutes, but some may have more decentralized systems with a greater role for local organizations and networks.

- The specific institutions participating in the AKIS system, such as government agencies, research institutes, universities, farmers' organizations, and private sector associations, vary from country to country. The degree of cooperation and partnership between these institutions also differs.

- Countries show varying levels of funding and resources to support AKIS activities. It affects research, services, technology transfer, and other parts of the knowledge and innovation system.

- National agricultural policies and priorities influence the focus areas of AKIS activities and research and innovation, focusing either on sustainable development, climate adaptation or rural development. In developed European countries (Germany, France) the first trend prevails, while elsewhere the socio-economic situation of farmers.

- Socio-economic factors, cultural norms, and historical context also determine the characteristics of AKIS in countries. The role of farmers' associations, the traditions of information exchange and the attitude to innovations are also different.

- There are regional differences in the operation and effectiveness of AKIS in various countries. Rural-urban differences, agricultural landscapes, and different levels of infrastructure and human capital reflect this inequality.

Consequently, weak and strong, integrated and fragmented networks and organizational systems were born for the transfer of knowledge and innovations. A strong AKIS is supported by strong actors, and dedicated resources and benefits farmers, while a weak AKIS lacks these features and advisory services reach farmers poorly. An integrated AKIS is managed by a coordinating authority and national policies that form the links to the system, while in a fragmented AKIS, several independent information networks work side by side, which are not well coordinated and usually compete with each other.

Determining these differences is an important prerequisite for researchers and stakeholders involved in policy-making and agricultural development and innovation so that strategies and activities can be effectively adapted to specific country contexts. Determining which EU countries have an advantage in terms of Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS) can be complex and subjective because it depends on several factors such as the agricultural sector of the country, research and innovation infrastructure, political environment, and socio-economic context and specific objectives.

However, some EU countries are often referred to as leaders or have significant strengths in agricultural research, innovation, and information exchange. These forces may be different according to the special characteristics of AKIS. For example, the Netherlands is known for its advanced agricultural sector and innovative farming methods. It has a highly developed research and innovation infrastructure, strong public-private partnerships, and a culture of information exchange and collaboration.

Netherlands agricultural research institutes and companies are known for their expertise in areas such as greenhouse technology, precision farming, and sustainable agricultural practices. The AKIS system in the Netherlands is considered very strong because the participants are strong and provide farmers with relevant knowledge and information.

Germany has a rich history of agricultural analysis and innovation. Germany's federal structure significantly impacts its AKIS. Agricultural policy and advisory services are largely decentralized, with substantial roles played by the federal states (Länder). This leads

to a diverse landscape of advisory services and research institutions that can differ widely in approach and focus from one state to another. The Chambers of Agriculture (Landwirtschaftskammern) play a crucial role in providing advisory services. These semi-public organizations are funded by both public money and farmers' membership fees. This model is less prevalent in other EU countries, where private consultancy or state services may dominate. Germany's AKIS is characterized by its integrated research and education system, robust farmer cooperatives, focus on sustainability, public-private partnerships, and emphasis on digital innovation, stringent regulatory framework, and export orientation. These elements collectively shape a distinctive agricultural knowledge and innovation landscape in Germany.

Denmark is known for its efficient and sustainable agricultural practices and strongly supports research and innovation. The country has an established network of agricultural extension services, research institutes, and farm cooperatives that facilitate information exchange and technology adoption. Danish agriculture is known for its emphasis on environmental sustainability, animal welfare, and food safety.

France has a diverse agricultural sector and is known for its agricultural research institutes and universities. It has a strong tradition of agricultural research and advisory services, as well as expertise in areas such as agronomy, viticulture, and agroecology. France also plays an important role in shaping the EU's agricultural policy and research program.

Ireland is known for providing AKIS through the highly integrated and unique national Teagasc, which combines research, development, and education. This is an example of an integrated AKIS system.

Although the UK will no longer be a member of the EU from 2021, it has historically played a key role in European agricultural research and innovation. It has world-class research facilities, such as Rothamsted Research, whose researchers publish more than 300 articles and innovations in popular journals every year. The UK has expertise in areas such as crop genetics, breeding, and agricultural economics.

In Eastern European countries (like Georgia) agricultural advice is given by all types of organizations and no particular group dominates. Local knowledge and informal networks are one of the most important sources of advice, especially among smallholders. Farmers' organizations or public organizations dominate agricultural advisory services in most EU countries, but there are also countries where private organizations are pioneers. A combination of several governing organizations is also common

Conclusion

AKIS is therefore a complex and dynamic system in which a large number of actors, both public and private, are interconnected in various ways. The success of the system depends on improved inter-sectoral relations, internal coordination, and inclusive participation of the private sector. The knowledge transfer and inno-

vation systems for farmers in EU countries differ, despite the common principles, but it is also important to consider that each country has its unique challenges, and the effectiveness of AKIS depends on many factors other than science and innovation. AKIS in EU countries is diverse and each country's model reflects its unique socio-political context, agricultural structure, and political priorities. AKIS can be more centralized (e.g. France), dependent on private consulting services (e.g. the Netherlands), or less integrated with research institutions (e.g. some Eastern European countries). But in principle, the dominant approach is the country's institutional readiness to address agricultural challenges and engage farmers in education to introduce modern innovative technologies.

References

1. EU SCAR AKIS (2019), Preparing for Future AKIS in Europe. Standing Committee on Agricultural Research (SCAR), 4th Report of the Strategic Working Group on Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS), Directorate-General for Agriculture and Rural Development, 2nd Edition, 2019, Brussels, European Commission, p. 12-13. https://scar-europe.org/images/AKIS/Documents/report-preparing-for-future-akis-in-europe_en.pdf
2. The World Bank (2003), Reaching the Rural Poor, A Renewed Strategy for Rural Development, <https://documents1.worldbank.org/curated/en/227421468165890144/pdf/267630REACHINGOTHEORURAL0POOR0.pdf>
3. EU Commission (2006), Putting Knowledge into Practice: A Broad Innovation Strategy for the European Union, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=COM:2006:0502:FIN:en:PDF>
4. WB (2012), Agricultural Innovation Systems: An Investment Sourcebook, International Bank for Reconstruction and Development, <https://documents1.worldbank.org/curated/en/140741468336047588/pdf/672070PUB0EPI0067844B09780821386842.pdf>
5. EU SCAR (2013), Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation System Towards 2020, An orientation paper on linking innovation and research, SCAR-Collaborative Working Group AKIS-2, Brussels, p. 204, https://scar-europe.org/images/AKIS/Documents/AKIS_toward_s_2020.pdf
6. European Commission (2023), Evaluating the AKIS Strategic Approach in CAP Strategic Plans, Guidelines, Directorate-General for Agriculture and Rural Development, Unit A.3, https://eu-cap-network.ec.europa.eu/publications/guidelines-evaluating-akis-strategic-approach-cap-strategic-plans_en#section--resources
7. European Commission's Putting Knowledge into Practice: A Broad Innovation Strategy for the European Union (2006). <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=COM:2006:0502:FIN:en:PDF>